

LOBED LEAVES IN MAIZE

Two Edges of Leaf Cut Each Other When Growing—Resultant Clefts Were Supposed by Blaringhem to be Due to Inheritance of a Mutilation

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IN 1911 there appeared in an early variety of maize from Russia what was thought to be a new abnormality. This was a pronounced lobing of the leaves on many of the plants, and as none of the grasses normally has lobed leaves, this character received careful attention.

As the season progressed, the abnormality was found in varying degrees on all of ninety varieties planted that season at Lanham, Md. The conspicuous nature of the lobes led to the belief that this must be their first appearance. This view was quickly dispelled when upon examining commercial plantings of local varieties many of the plants were found to have lobed leaves. In following seasons lobes recurred not only in Maryland, but in many other localities where opportunity for examination was presented. They were also found on plants of *Euchlaena*, *Coix*, *Tripsacum* and various members of the *Andropogoneæ*, and doubtless occur on many other grasses.

The superficial resemblance of lobes to torn leaves must account for the fact that they had escaped detection in previous years. Careful observation, however, reveals pronounced differences between lobed and split leaves, and once these are recognized, there can be no confusion of the two forms of injury.

The lobes are usually paired, one on each side of the leaf and nearly opposite. This is not always the case, however, as several leaves with only one lobe have been found and a few with as many as six lobes.

The most constant characteristics of true lobes are the margins, which are transparent like those of a normal leaf, and are beset with long brittle hairs and a double row of short saw-like teeth

directed toward the apex of the leaf. The edges of torn leaves lack these teeth and the marginal cells are dead. Lobes are also sometimes spatulate in form, with the margin at the base of the split thickened and rounded.

The veins frequently divide a short distance below the split, one branch continuing to the main blade, the other to the lobe. The veins that do not divide alter their course below the split, making a curve which enables them to reach the lobe. The presence of normal marginal tissue, together with the blunt or spatulate form of many of the lobes, indicates that the formation of the lobes takes place at a very early stage in the development of the leaf.

The lobing often results in a complete entanglement of the leaves, so that the plant is prevented from growing in a normal manner and in extreme cases the upper leaves and tassel never emerge. Plants thus affected have a characteristic "bent over" shape.

LOBING OF OTHER ORGANS

The occurrence of lobing is not confined to the leaf blades of the main culm and tillers, but has also been frequently observed on other homologous organs of the plant. The most common among these are the husks, husk leaves, and the glumes of the tassel. In this latter case the lobes are very small, but are undoubtedly of the same nature as those on the leaf blades.

A slightly modified type of lobing is also found on prophylla. The abnormality in this case could hardly be called lobing, but is in reality notching. These notches are in pairs on opposite sides of the prophylla, much the same as the lobes on the blades.

Lobes approximating in shape those

THE "LOBES" OF MAIZE LEAVES

The edges of the leaf sometimes cut each other as they grow, thus producing this deceptive appearance of lobing. The veins of the leaf rearrange themselves, as may be seen in the lower left-hand corner of the picture, to conform to the changed condition of affairs. This abnormality is not very rare, although it has seldom been noticed. Blaringhem, who mutilated maize plants to see if he could produce an inherited effect, found these "lobes" in the progeny, and wrongly supposed that they were due to his manipulations. Photograph natural size. (Fig. 11.)

on the leaves are occasionally found on the keels of prophylla, though they are usually small and poorly formed.

It was at first thought that the lobing of the leaves was a purely local abnormality directly due to some climatic disturbance much as is the leaf cut or Tomosis of Cotton. However, the observations of Blaringhem in France and Gernert in Illinois demonstrate beyond doubt that forms of lobing have a wide distribution.¹ Investigation also shows that lobing not only occurs on experimental varieties outside their natural environment, but is found in about the same percentage in commercial plantings in many localities.

The cause of the lobing was not fully understood until in dissecting some very small lateral branches of *Euchlaena* it was noticed that several of the shoots were prevented from unfurling by having the margins of one of the leaf blades firmly held together with lobes. By examining still smaller shoots, the stage was finally reached where the lobes were just being formed. These shoots were about 6 cm. long and the tissue was exceedingly tender. It was at once seen that the lobes were formed by the margins of the leaf blades cutting each other where they crossed in unfurling.

The forcing of the inside margin of the leaf against the outside margin results in the inside margin being cut, but at the same time the outside

margin also receives a slight cut through which the lobe on the inside margin grows. As this lobe grows it cuts upward into the outside margin which accounts for the small back cut sometimes found on one margin of the more perfect specimens. A slight rupture of the tissue, which at this young stage is extremely tender, results in the separated cells developing practically independent of the remainder of the leaf blade.

The fact that the two margins of the same leaf mutually rupture each other accounts for the lobes being most often found in pairs one on each side of the leaf.

Lobes are not always made by the margins of the same leaf, but are sometimes made by the margins of adjoining leaves. In this way a single lobe on only one side of the leaf is brought about. Frequently when the margin of a leaf comes in contact with another leaf immediately inside of it the result is an opening in the leaf which develops marginal tissue on each edge. The marginal teeth, if examined at an early stage, are seen to be about half the size of the teeth on the outside margins of the blade.

The comparatively late stage in the development of the leaf at which lobing takes place, demonstrates that the cells normally forming the body of the leaf blade are capable of being transformed into the specialized marginal tissue.

Mutations in the Potato

It has sometimes been alleged that the characters of wild species of potato are immutable, but J. Aumiot, who has been breeding many of them, reports changes of many kinds, in *C. R. Acad. Agric.*, November, 1915, summarized in the *International Review of Agriculture*. Aside from changes of simple characters like color, there were sup-

posed mutations which affected the time of maturity, the character of the skin, the growth habit, and the flowers. In one instance a plant of *Solanum commersoni* is alleged to have been transformed so that it closely resembled a cultivated variety. The study of such cases as this might throw much light on the process of evolution.

¹ The first notice of these lobed leaves which I have found is by L. Blaringhem in *Mutation et Traumatismes* (Paris, 1908). Blaringhem mutilated maize plants in various ways and then grew their seed; the resulting plants showed various abnormalities, such as cleft leaves, which he thought were due to his mutilation of the parents. When other observers discovered the same abnormalities in maize plants whose parents had not been mutilated, Blaringhem's effort to revive the inheritance of acquired characters came to nothing. Since then Gernert mentioned lobed or cleft leaves as one of the many abnormalities to be found in maize, but gave no explanation of their origin. ("The Analysis of Characters in Corn and their Behavior in Transmission," p. 25, Champaign, Ill., 1912.)